

Quantum Efficiency of the Photo-reduction of Alcoholic Solutions of Ferric Chloride.

BY MATA PRASAD AND P. S. LIMAYE.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 91) it has been shown that for the first four hours the order of the photo-reduction of alcoholic solutions of ferric chloride in artificial light is zero molecular. In the present investigation the quantum efficiency of the photo-reduction of ferric chloride has been studied in radiations of different wave-lengths at different temperatures. The effect of the concentration of the solution on the quantum efficiency has also been studied and the applicability of the Einstein's Law of photochemical equivalence has been discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement was the same as described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). The quantum efficiency was studied at three different temperatures, 30°, 38°, and 45°. The temperature was maintained constant by an electrically heated air thermostat within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The reaction cell was well protected from the radiations from the heater by means of a black screen interposed between the reaction cell and the heater. It was observed from the absorption photographs of ferric chloride solutions in ethyl alcohol that complete absorption between 4000Å and 5000Å takes place if the concentration of the solution is not less than 0.08M. Consequently solutions of concentrations greater than 0.08M were used for the measurements of quantum efficiency. The quantum efficiency was studied in the radiations 4000Å–5000Å (mean value 4500Å) and 4580Å–4940Å (mean value 4760Å). These radiations were obtained by using the following solution filters:

(a) 2.716N CuSO_4 + 0.01 g. methyl violet in 100 c. c. of water, each in 1 cm. thickness. Transmission 4000Å – 5000Å.

(b) CuSO_4 aq., 150 g./litre 2 cm. thickness + methyl green aq. 0.1 g./litre 2 cm. thickness. Transmission 4580Å – 4940Å.

The amount of reduction was measured by titrating the solution with $N/100$ -dichromate solution using diphenylamine as an internal indicator.

To measure the light energy absorbed by the solution, the galvanometric deflections obtained by exposing a large surface thermopile connected to a sensitive galvanometer were first calibrated in terms of Hefner-100. The energy in Hefner-100 absorbed by the solution was then calculated from the deflections of the galvanometer for pure alcohol and for the solution of ferric chloride in that alcohol.

The number of molecules changed per sq. cm. per sec. was calculated from the titration data using the formula,

$$N \times n \times t \times A$$

where N is the Avogadro's constant (6.06×10^{23}), n the number of g. molecules of ferric chloride reduced in time t , expressed in seconds and A (7 sq. cm.), the area of the solution, illuminated by light.

The number of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. is given by the formula,

$$e \times 900 \times \lambda \times 10^{-8} / 3 \times 10^{10} \times 6.5 \times 10^{-27}$$

where e is the absorption in Hefner-100 and λ the mean wavelength of the filter in Angstrom units.

The quantum efficiency Q was calculated from

$$Q = \frac{\text{No. of molecules changed}}{\text{No. of quanta absorbed}}$$

TABLE I.

Solution in pure methyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.188M.

Mean wave-length = 4500Å.			Mean wave-length = 4760Å.		
Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.	Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.
30°	1.31	1.28	30°	1.53	0.78
38°	1.7	1.61	38°	1.65	1.18
45°		2.86	45°		1.89

TABLE II.

Solution in pure methyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.094M.

Mean wave-length = 4500Å.			Mean wave-length = 4760Å.		
Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.	Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.
30°	...	0.64	30°	...	0.32
	1.1			1.7	
38°		0.68	38°		0.63
	2.7			2.2	
45°		1.91	45°		1.125

TABLE III.

Solution in anhydrous ethyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.19M.

Mean wave-length = 4500Å.			Mean wave-length = 4760Å.		
Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.	Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.
30°		1.24	30°		0.49
	1.2			1.3	
38°		1.55	38°		0.613
	1.8			2.04	
45°		2.77	45°		1.25

TABLE IV.

Solution in anhydrous ethyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.095M.

Mean wave-length = 4500Å.			Mean wave-length = 4760Å.		
Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.	Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.
30°		0.58	30°		0.2
	1.2			1.5	
38°		0.69	38°		0.27
	2.4			1.7	
45°		1.89	45°		0.48

TABLE V.

Solution in n-propyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.155M.

Mean wave-length = 4500Å.			Mean wave-length = 4760Å.		
Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.	Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.
30°	1.23	2.98	30°	1.3	0.59
38°	1.1	3.67	38°	1.1	0.77
45°		3.98	45°		0.892

TABLE VI.

Solution in n-propyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.08M.

Mean wave-length = 4500Å.			Mean wave-length = 4760Å.		
Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.	Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.
30°	1.23	1.55	30°	1.3	0.34
38°	1.03	2.2	38°	1.1	0.443
45°		2.26	45°		0.48

TABLE VII.

Solution in n-butyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.165M.

Mean wave-length = 4500Å.			Mean wave-length = 4760Å.		
Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.	Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.
30°	1.46	2.5	30°	1.03	0.75
38°	1.2	3.64	38°	1.0	0.772
45°		4.34	45°		0.82

TABLE VIII.

Solution in n-butyl alcohol.

Conc. of the solution = 0.082M.

Mean wave-length = 4500Å.			Mean wave-length = 4760Å.		
Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.	Temp.	Temp. coeff.	Q.
30°		1.907	30°		0.56
	1.0			1.0	
38°		1.91	38°		0.501
	1.2			0.92	
45°		2.26	45°		0.56

DISCUSSION.

It will be seen from the foregoing tables that the quantum efficiency in dilute solutions is much less than that in the concentrated ones and that at the same temperature the quantum efficiency of the same solution is greater in light of lower wave-lengths and it increases as the temperature is raised. The results are in agreement with those usually obtained in photochemical reactions (*cf.* Dhar and Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 143; Mukerji and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 6, 1790; and Allmand, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1652).

It is also apparent from the tables that the quantum efficiency of the photo-reduction of ferric chloride in different alcohols varies from nearly 0.6 to 4. It appears therefore that Einstein's Law is valid approximately in the present case. The primary effect of the absorption of a light quantum appears to be the excitation of the ferric chloride molecules which break up into ferrous chloride and chlorine. No other side reaction seems to take place during the first two hours of the starting of the reaction.

The authors are very thankful to Mr. S. M. Mehta, B.A., M.Sc. for his kind assistance.

